

QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES PART VI.

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For obvious pharmacological reasons, a pyridino-quinoline derivative has been synthesised. The condensation product of $\alpha\alpha'$ -phenylcarbamylacetone dicarboxylate and an aromatic amine could not be cyclised to a piperidine derivative.

In order to study factors necessary for antiplasmodial action King *et al* (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1938, **B128**, 49, 60) prepared some quinoly-piperidyl-carbinols, which approach nearly the quinine structure. It was thought of considerable interest to synthesise a compound in which a pyridine ring is fused with the quinoline residue and to see if such a compound possesses any antimalarial properties.

The action of amines on ethyl $\alpha\alpha'$ -phenylcarbamylacetone dicarboxylate (Ghosh and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 355) has now been found to yield the compound (I) and not a piperidine derivative (*cf.* Ruhemann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, **65**, 259, 874 ; *Ber.*, 1894, **27**, 1272). All attempts to convert (I) into a piperidine derivative have failed, possibly due to the presence of the keto group.

The NO_2 group in 3:5-*o*-nitrobenzylidene-2:4:6-triketopiperidine derivative (II) (Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 694) could not be reduced by zinc dust and acetic acid to yield a piperidine-quinoline derivative.

2:4-Dihydroxy-3-carbethoxy-6-methylpyridine (Knoevenagel and Fries, *Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 768 ; 1902, **35**, 2893) has now been allowed to react with aniline at 170°, when the anilide (III) is obtained. When treated with concentrated sulphuric acid, the compound (III) furnishes the sulphonated substance (IV) in which a pyridine ring is fused with the quinoline residue.

EXPERIMENTAL.

αα'-*m*-Tolylcarbamylic acid dianilide (I, R = *m*-tolyl).— A mixture of ethyl *αα'*-phenylcarbamylic acid dicarboxylate (4.4 g.) and *m*-toluidine (2.2 g.) was heated in an oil-bath at 160–170° for 4 hours, when alcohol was eliminated. The solid obtained was powdered and washed successively with dilute alkali, dilute hydrochloric acid and water. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellow rectangular plates, m. p. 206–7°, yield 3 g. (Found: N, 10.12. C₂₃H₂₀O₅N₄ requires N, 9.96 per cent).

Whereas ethyl *αα'*-phenylcarbamylic acid dicarboxylate readily condenses with aldehydes in acetic acid solution (*cf.* Ghosh and Guha, *loc. cit.*; Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 693), the compound (I) does not condense with aldehydes under similar conditions.

αα'-*p*-Tolylcarbamylic acid dianilide (I, R = *p*-tolyl) was prepared in a similar manner. The product crystallised from glacial acetic acid in light orange rectangular plates, m. p. 222–23°. (Found: N, 10.04. C₂₃H₂₀O₅N₄ requires N, 9.96 per cent). It is insoluble in dilute alkali and dilute acids.

2:4-Dihydroxy-3-phenylcarbamido-6-methylpyridine (II).— A mixture of 2:4-dihydroxy-3-carbomethoxy-6-methylpyridine (9.8 g.) and aniline (4.7 g.) was heated in an oil-bath at 170° for 8 hours. The pasty mass was triturated with acetic acid and the solid was then filtered and washed several times with acetic acid. It was crystallised first from glacial acetic acid and then from benzene in colourless rectangular plates, m. p. 279–80°, yield 4 g. (Found: N, 10.99. C₁₃H₁₁O₃N₂ requires N, 11.47 per cent). It gives a reddish colouration with ferric chloride.

2-Hydroxy-6-methylpyridino-3:4 (3':4')-2-hydroxyquinoline Disulphonic Acid (IV).— The above compound (II, 6 g.) was heated with concentrated sulphuric acid (30 c. c.) in an oil-bath at 100° for 45 minutes. Effervescence was noticed in the reaction mixture, which was allowed to cool and poured into ice-cold water. The mixture was then partially neutralised with sodium bicarbonate. The solid, thus obtained, was crystallised several times from

hot water (charcoal) in colourless crystalline powder, m. p. above 300° , yield 2 g. The compound is strongly acid in reaction and is readily soluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution. That this compound is a sulphonic acid derivative and not a sulphate is proved by the fact that it remains unaffected when treated with aqueous sodium acetate solution. The equivalent weight of this disulphonic acid derivative was determined by titration with standard baryta and the molecular weight was determined. It does not form an oxime and does not give any distinctive colouration with ferric chloride. [Found: C, 39.02; H, 3.74; N, 6.77; S, 15.68, 15.34; H_2O , 4.19; M.W. (by titration), 400. $C_{12}H_{10}O_8N_2S_2 \cdot H_2O$ requires C, 38.61; H, 2.97; N, 6.93; S, 15.84; H_2O , 4.45 per cent.; M.W., 404]. The molecule of water is tenaciously held and is removed completely when the substance is heated at $155-165^{\circ}$ in *vacuo* for about 16 hours. The substance is soluble in cold concentrated hydrochloric acid and is precipitated as a gelatinous mass on dilution with water, which shows that it has got feeble basicity and does not form a stable hydrochloride. Even on boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid; the hydrochloride could not be obtained. The sodium salt of this compound may, however, prove to be suitable for pharmacological examination. It was contemplated to prepare the acetyl derivative of the compound, from which the corresponding acid chloride and amide could be obtained. The acetyl derivative was, however, obtained as a pasty mass, which could not be crystallised and obtained pure.

The *picrate* was obtained as yellow needles, which began to change to brown at 217° and ultimately became black above 300° .

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